

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Propiophenone and Butyrophenone by *N*-Bromosaccharin in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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The title reaction has been studied in aqueous acetic acid medium in presence of $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$. Order with respect to substrate, oxidant and $[\text{H}^+]$ is one in each. Added saccharin retards the rate of reaction. The reaction system did not induce polymerisation of added acrylonitrile indicating the absence of free radicals in the system. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. The order of reactivity among the two substrates studied is propiophenone > butyrophenone. A suitable mechanism consistent with the observed results is proposed.

THE oxidation of aliphatic¹ and aryl aliphatic ketones by *N*-bromosaccharin (NBS) shows that in case of aliphatic ketones irrespective of chain length, the reaction proceeds through the enol formation as the rate determining step. In our earlier paper on the kinetics of oxidation of acetophenones² by NBSaccharin, we discussed the effect of substituents on the benzene ring. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the effect of chain length of the alkyl group in the aryl aliphatic ketone on rate and mechanism, and also to study the order of reactivity of the substrates in order to find out which form of the species of oxidant is involved in the reaction.

Experimental

Propiophenone (Koch-light) and butyrophenone (Aldrich) were used as such. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and purified further either by recrystallisation or by distillation. The oxidant was prepared by the bromination of saccharin³. The reactions were carried out under the conditions of $[\text{substrate}] \gg [\text{NBS}]$ in acetic acid-water mixture in presence of 0.004 M $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ at the specified H_2SO_4 concentration in the temperature range 20–45°. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating unreacted oxidant iodometrically¹.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometric study of the reaction shows that two moles of the oxidant are required to oxidise one mole of substrate¹.

The products are identified as the corresponding diketones. The bromide ions are detected by the usual method. The Br^- ion formed is complexed by adding $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ to avoid oxidation by bromine. The rate of reaction was studied at various oxidant concentrations. A plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time is a straight line indicating order with respect to oxidant is one. But at the same time the k_{obs} values decrease with increase in $[\text{NBSaccharin}]^{4,5}$. This decrease may be due to the presence of unreactive species which increases at higher [oxidant] leading to the decrease of active oxidant concentration. The reaction has been carried out at different [substrate] ranging from 0.01 to 0.03 M. It is found that the rate is linearly dependent on [substrate] (Table 1). A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{substrate}]$ is a straight line with unit slope indicating that the order with

TABLE 1— k_{obs} VALUES FOR PROPIO/BUTYROPHENONE—NBSACCHARIN SYSTEM

$[\text{NBSac}] = 0.002 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 0.002 \text{ M}$, Temp. = 318 K, $\text{HOAc}-\text{H}_2\text{O} = 50\% (\text{v/v})$

[Substrate] M	[Sacch] M	[H ⁺] M	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$	
			Propiophenone	Butyrophenone
0.01	—	0.1	1.71	1.67
0.02	—	0.1	3.41	3.34
0.04	—	0.1	7.31	5.91
0.06	—	0.1	11.29	9.20
0.08	—	0.1	15.35	12.79
0.02	—	0.05	1.77	1.42
0.02	—	0.20	7.11	5.69
0.02	—	0.30	10.10	8.93
0.02	—	0.40	13.80	10.66
0.02	0.001	0.1	3.41	3.34
0.02	0.002	0.1	2.33	1.83
0.02	0.004	0.1	1.63	1.13
0.02	0.006	0.1	1.32	0.83
0.02	0.01	0.1	1.02	0.51

respect to substrate is one. A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/(\text{substrate})$ is a straight line passing through the

origin indicating the absence of complex formation between oxidant and substrate. The rate of reaction has been studied at various $[H_2SO_4]$ ranging from 0.05 to 0.4 M (Table 1). A plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [H_2SO_4]$ is a straight line with a unit slope indicating first order dependence on [Acid]. The rate of oxidation for propio- and butyro-phenones were determined at different temperatures ranging from 20 to 45°. From the slopes of the plots of $\log k_{II}$ vs $1/T$, activation parameters were evaluated and are given in Table 2. The rate of reaction is not affected

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

[NBS]=0.002 M, [Substrate]=0.02 M, $[Hg(OAc)_2]=0.002$ M, Temp.=318 K, HOAc-H₂O=50% (v/v), $[H_2SO_4]=0.1$ M,

Substrate	k_{II} $\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Propiophenone	17.06	52.08	115.6	89.1
Butyrophenone	16.71	61.20	88.6	89.3

$k_{II} = k_{obs}/[\text{Substrate}]$.

by the addition of $Hg(OAc)_2$ and also by the addition of Na_2SO_4 . The reaction failed to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile showing that the free radicals are not formed during the course of reaction. The effect of added saccharin on the rate of reaction has been carried out at different [Saccharin] (Table 1). The rate decreases with increase in [Saccharin]. A plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [\text{Saccharin}]$ is a straight line with negative slope which is less than one. This indicates that saccharin is formed in a pre-equilibrium step along with another step in which saccharin is not formed. The oxidation rates of these two substrates were found to be faster than the corresponding bromination rates, thus ruling out the possibility of enol form being involved in the slow step. The possible active species of the oxidant are NBSacc, NBSaccH⁺, HOBr, H_2O^+Br and Br^+ . The retarding effect of added [Saccharin] on rate indicates that protonated form of saccharin is not reactive species. If the oxidant is assumed to react in the form of Br^+ or H_2O^+Br , it should be with keto form of substrate only. According to Littler⁷ one-electron oxidants attack the keto form. The added acrylonitrile failed to show any evidence regarding the presence of one-electron steps and at the same time it is known that N-halo compounds behave only as two-electron oxidants. Thus, the participation of keto form may be ruled out. With aforementioned kinetic observation, protonated form of the ketone reacts with HOBr and the free oxidant in the rate determining step. The following mechanism is suggested for these two ketones.

The following rate law can be derived,

$$\text{Rate} = K_1 [\text{Ketone}] [H^+] [\text{Oxidant}] [k_1 K_2 / [\text{Saccharin}] + k_2] \quad (6)$$

The rate expression explains the observed kinetic parameters like first order with respect to [Substrate], $[H^+]$ and [NBSacc], and the rate retardation due to added saccharin. The order of reactivity among these two substrates indicates that propiophenone > butyrophenone. The lower reactivity of butyrophenone can be attributed to steric factor.

The kinetics of oxidation of acetophenone^a under identical conditions of propio- and butyrophenones reveal that except the effect of saccharin on rate, other kinetic observations are similar. In acetophenone, the order with respect to saccharin is zero, while in the present system the rate depends on the concentration of saccharin in a complex way. This indicates that though these three substrates are of similar type except the length of the alkyl group, they appear to influence the nature of reactive species of oxidant. Even a slight change in the electron density at the reaction centre appears to change the nature of the active species which in turn effect the influence of [Saccharin] on rate. In case of acetophenone oxidation by NBSacc^a, steps (2) and (3) of the mechanism are deleted and in the rate expression (equation 6) the first term is deleted.

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References

1. K. V. MOHAN, P. R. RAO and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 225, 876.
2. K. V. MOHAN, P. R. RAO and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Proc National Acad. Sci, India*, 1987, communicated.
3. J. N. BACCHAWAT and N. K. MATHUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1335.
4. G. GOPALAKRISHNA, B. R. PAI and N. V. SUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem, Sect. B*, 1979, **18**, 92.
5. C. P. SUBAS and B. R. DEV, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 165.
6. V. MANOHARAN and N. V. SUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem, Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 165.
7. J. S. LITTLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 827.